

THE SIGNIFICANCE OF THE DOCTRINE OF CONFUCIUS IN WORLD
PEDAGOGY

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ANNOTATION

In the pedagogical views of Confucius, respect for the rules existing in the society was also in the main place. In society, all order based on humanity (Jen) - discipline is said to have come down from heaven, and everyone must obey it. Confucian views are expressed in the concept of "li". Without "li" in society, there will be no order, order - the opinion that there is no development where there is no discipline occupies a central place in Confucian teachings.

Key words: Confucian teachings, China, discipline, philosophy, ancient world, world pedagogy.

INTRODUCTION

The teachings of the philosophical schools formed in ancient China are gaining importance in China and several other countries of the East. At this point, it is necessary to emphasize the role of Confucianism. When I heard that Confucius' teaching should be read and learned by all mankind, I thought it was nonsense. But now I am beginning to understand that most of the enlightened people in Europe and America seem to be gradually coming to this idea. According to European scientists, Western nations have achieved four basic rules during their three hundred years of development: to be selfish; to kill others; to be correct in small amounts; to feel less shame. As different as the basic principles of Confucius and Meng-tzu are, Heaven and Earth are just as vast and deep, composed to do good to all and everywhere.

In China, the school created by Confucius lasted for many centuries. In 136 BC, during the reign of Emperor Wu-Di, Confucian views were officially declared as a doctrine - a system. After that, the teachings of Confucius continued as a dominant idea for more than two thousand years. We can see Confucius' opinions about man in his work "Conversations and Reflections", which reflects his conversations with his students. Jamiyatda sodir bo'layotgan turli axloqsizliklardan Konfutsiy qattiq tashvishga tushadi, fuqarolarni tarbiyalashga harakat qilib, ularni insof-diyonatga, bir-birlarini hurmat qilishga, atrof-muhit musaffoligini ta'minlashga chorlaydi. Uning tushuntirishicha, insoniylikning turli fazilatlarini o'zida mujassamlashtirgan chinakam inson faqat o'zi uchun emas, balki jamiyat uchun, boshqalar uchun ham yashamog'i darkor. The humanity of a person must first of all meet the following requirements. For example:

- a) help others in every possible way to achieve the success you dream of;
- b) don't impose on others the problems you don't want to happen to yourself.

The views of Confucius later played an important role in the development of moral principles, ideals of justice, brotherhood, and freedom in world philosophy. This doctrine was raised to the level of the state religion in China for two thousand years and gained great importance in the life of the people. Even today, the calls of our ancestors to preserve the Motherland, nature, society, and not to violate its rules and regulations have not become obsolete. The passage of years and centuries does not reduce their value. After all, these teachings are about universal human values that cannot be burned in fire or water.

Ancient Chinese philosophers tried to explain that the daily practical activities of a person can be managed with the help of educational and moral norms, especially that education and discipline are important in the formation of human qualities in a person, and that the natural and social environment is a decisive factor in the development of a person. According to Confucianism, the law should serve human interests.

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